

LONG RANGE POLLUTION DISPERSION

WEATHER SERVICES AND PRODUCTS FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

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The Met.Office

The Nuclear Accident Response Model - NAME

INTRODUCTION :

After the Chernobyl accident in late April 1986, it became clear that there was very definite need for a model that could assess the possible risks to the public due to airborne radioactive pollutants. Consequently, the Met Office began to develop a model that could analyse the distribution of materials, that when released in the atmosphere could pose a hazard over hundreds or thousands of kilometres, whether they be radioactive, chemical or biological. Such a model would have to simulate the transport and deposition of an airborne pollutant by using as much meteorological data and information about the release as possible. It should also be capable of analysing actual or forecast data.

At the same time, plans were being made by the Government to produce a more effective response to such incidents. The Met Office made their intentions known and it was decided to incorporate the model development as a recognised part of the Governments plans. The model soon became an official part of the Department of Environments national response plan in the event of an accidental release of radionuclides. This way the Government could benefit from the model's predictions, for example, by providing information regarding the areas where high levels of activity were expected. Decisions about any restrictions on food consumption could then be made.

The model, developed by the Met. Office is known by the acronym "NAME".

MODEL TITLE :

- * The Nuclear Accident Response Model - NAME

MODEL TYPE :

- * Long range atmospheric dispersion model based on a Lagrangian techniques. That is to say, NAME will simulate the spread of airborne pollutants by releasing particles into the 'model atmosphere' and allowing them to be passively carried along by the winds and spread by small scale diffusion.

MODEL USES :

- * Although originally designed to simulate the dispersion of airborne radionuclides, the model can be used for a variety of operational or research purposes.
- * The particles released by the model may 'carry' toxic pollutants, volcanic effluents or nothing at all, and simply be used to investigate large scale diffusion.

MODEL RESOLUTION :

- * NAME currently uses a 50km grid resolution with a 16km grid version under development.

SPECIAL FEATURES :

- * NAME can utilize up to 6 different levels in the vertical, the lowest of which is the atmospheric boundary layer.
- * Rainfall remains one of the most effective ways by which airborne pollutants are removed from the atmosphere (there is a high correlation between deposition and rainfall amount over the UK following the Chernobyl incident). NAME incorporates the use of very highly resolved precipitation fields which will produce a far more accurate deposition value, and a better indication of where potential "hot spots" are likely to occur.

OUTPUT :

The following diagrams give an indication of the types of output extracted from the model. The diagrams show an example of a notional accidental release of Caesium-137 on the coast at Cornwall. For this example, it is assumed that a release of 100TBq per hour took place at 1200 GMT on the 17/9/93 and that it is continuous. The output shows the particle trajectory end points at 1200 on 19/9/93 first in the boundary layer and then within layer 3 of the model (layer 3 lies in the range 0.93 to 0.87 of the surface pressure). The next diagram shows the air concentration in Bequerel per meter cubed, followed by the wet and dry deposition in kilo-Bequerel per meter squared.

The same information is then given for the situation at 1200 on the 21/9/93.

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
WINDCAST TRAJECTORY END POINTS IN BOUNDARY LAYER

RELEASE FROM 1200GMT 17/09/1993 CONTINUING
AT 500M 005 00M

12 Z SUN 19/09/1993

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
WINDCAST TRAJECTORY END POINTS IN LAYER 3

RELEASE FROM 1200GMT 17/09/1993 - CONTINUING
AT 50 00N 005 00W

12 Z SUN 19/09/1993

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
 WINDCAST AIR CONCENTRATION (BQ/M³) OF CAESIUM-137 IN GROUNDWATER LAYER

RELEASE FROM 1:00GMT 17/09/1993 CONTINUING

AT 50 00M 005 00M

WARNING: DEFAULT EMISSION PROFILE USED

12 Z SUN 19/09/1993

60

40

-10

-20

0

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
 HINDCAST ACCUMULATED WET DEPOSITION (KBO/M²) FOR CAESIUM-137

RELEASE FROM 1200GMT 17/09/1993 - CONTINUING

AT 50 00N 005 00W

WARNING: DEFAULT EMISSION PROFILE USED

12 7 SUN 19/09/1993

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
 WINDCAST ACCUMULATED DRY DEPOSITION INMBD/M-21 FOR CAESIUM-137

RELEASE FROM LOGRHT 17/09/1993 - CONTINUING
 C. 50 00N 00E UOM

12 Z SUN 19/09/1993

WARNING: DIFFICULT EMISSION PROFILE USED

10 20

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
WINDCAST TRAJECTORY END POINTS IN BOUNDARY LAYER

RELEASE FROM 1200GMT 17/09/1993 CONTINUING
AT 50 00N 005 00W

12 Z TUES 21/09/1993

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
WINDCAST TRAJECTORY END POINTS IN LATER 3

RELEASE FROM 1200GMT 17/09/1993 . CONTINUING
AT 50 00H 005 00H

12 Z TUES 21/09/1993

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
HINDCAST AIR CONCENTRATION (BQ/M³) OF CAESIUM-137 IN BOUNDARY LAYER

RELEASE FROM 1200GMT 17/09/1993 - CONTINUING

AT 50 00N 005 00W

WARNING: DEFAULT EMISSION PROFILE USED

12 2 TUES 21/09/1993

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
HINDCAST ACCUMULATED NET DEPOSITION (KBD/M²) FOR CAESIUM-137

RELEASE FROM 1200GMT 17/09/1993 - CONTINUING
AT 50 00M 005 00M

WARNING: DEFAULT EMISSION PROFILE USED

12 Z TUES 21/09/1993

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE NUCLEAR ACCIDENT RESPONSE MODEL
HINDCAST ACCUMULATED DRY DEPOSITION (KBD/M²) FOR CAESIUM-137

RELEASE FROM 1200GMT 17/09/1993 - CONTINUING

AT 50 00N 005 00W

WARNING: DEFAULT EMISSION PROFILE USED

12 Z TUES 21/09/1993

